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THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF FILIPINO SPECIAL EDUCATION TEACHERS IN CAMBODIA: A TRANSITION THEORY PERSPECTIVE

Danilo Ciceron T. Yabut

SPED Teacher

danyabut@gmail.com

College of Graduate School

Master of Arts in Education, Major in Special Education

National University, Manila, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This paper explored the plight and experiences of Filipino expatriates as special needs teachers in Cambodia, anchored on Schlossberg's Transition Theory, a concept that explains people's reaction to any form of change, and their capacity to handle such modifications (1995). A qualitative research design used the phenomenology approach and the four S key factors from the Transition Theory that has proven to be useful in understanding the motivations, challenges, and adaptive measures administered by Filipino SPED educators in a foreign land, and what measures are deemed necessary to address these multicultural concerns as basis for the design of a psychosocial program. Through the thematic analysis conducted, four emanant themes were determined with conclusive subthemes: (1) The Filipino Special Education Teachers' Motivations for Moving In based on the four S of Transition, (2) Psychosocial Challenges and Adaptations, (3) Psychosocial Coping Strategies, and (4) Psychosocial Supports: Needs and Recommendations. . Insights acquired from the study include motivations for moving, adaptive strategies and factors, support provided, perceptions and reality of migration, and coping mechanisms. The outcome of the study revealed the conditions, challenges, needs, inclinations, interests, and dreams of Filipino special education teachers in a foreign land and the fundamental psychosocial program that should be extended to them. The study amplifies the continuing discourse on the provision of providing adequate professional developmental opportunities, support and reinforcement programs to overseas educators through empirical findings and imperative courses of action from policymakers, school proprietors, stakeholders, and support organizations.

Keywords: *Lived Experiences, Moving in, Moving through, Psychosocial Support, Strategy, Support, Transition, SPED Filipino teachers*

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